

Investment Activities Of Insurance Companies: The Role Of Insurance Companies In The Financial Market

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Annotation: This article represents the investment activities of insurance companies of today and their place in the global financial market. It is well known that the role of insurance companies in overcoming losses in the economy, which is one of the most pressing problems in today's modern market economy, is invaluable. The insurance and investment processes they undertake can have a direct impact on the economic growth of countries, or vice versa. Therefore, important statistics are compared based on the scope of the topic. The article also discusses the current capitalization of insurance companies and their share in the financial market. There are also estimates of several countries on the placement and use of insurance reserves. In the end, suggestions and conclusions are given based on the research.

Keywords: Insurance companies, investment activities, financial relations, insurance activities, world economy, international relations, financial intermediaries, financial resources, economic losses, capital inflows.

Introduction: Insurance has been a paramount factor influencing the economy as an integral part of financial relations in the evolutionary stages of human history. In the current process of globalization, the innovative development of the insurance market is undergoing rapid changes, which makes it important to pay special attention to these processes and take them seriously. The insurance market is a key segment of the economy of any developed and developing country, but also directly contributes to its development.

It should be noted that insurance is a social phenomenon that is unique and widely used, and is a factor of stability. The activities of insurance companies play an important role in the formation of insurance activities and their growth in the world economy. Insurance companies are very important players in the global financial market as institutional investors, especially in the capital market. They play a vital role in implementing strong corporate governance, allocating financial market resources internationally, contributing to strong competition in the financial market, and balancing market levels at key times. The importance of insurance companies in capital markets is characterized by the following investment principles and available sources of funding in modern financial markets: Globalized, integrated, regulatory and emerging institutions. [1] Over the past five years, as a result of capital turnover and globalization in the insurance market, the following cases have been observed:

✚ increase in the concentration of insurance capitalization, in the process of which in the event of merger of insurers and reinsurers due to the merger or merger of multinational insurance companies in the global insurance market coverage was observed to be expanding;

✚ Integrated systematization and cooperation of insurance, banking and financial capital at the international level, contributed to the formation of transnational insurance companies;

✚ increased focus on risk research as an important factor in insurance risk management;

✚ The role of the Internet - a new mechanism for selling insurance services to consumers in an unstable market environment which is growing; [2]

Today, as a result of natural disasters and pandemics, various acts of sabotage, and the inability to find a place in today's competitive market, the demand for insurance companies is growing. As a result, as the share of insurance companies in the global financial market increases, they are taking market leadership and have every opportunity to win over other

industries. As people's self-insurance reflex grows, insurance companies are accumulating billions of dollars in financial resources. Thus, they are becoming major players in the global capital market and have a major impact on price changes in these markets.

Analysis of the literature used: The insurance industry is one of the central issues for the development of the economy, because, first of all, insurance companies serve as institutional investors in the stock markets, as well as accumulate large financial resources and increase the efficiency of additional activities. minladi. Insurance companies, which act as investors, are intermediaries in attracting the funds of individuals and legal entities to the stock market and remain one of the most stable sources of increasing their and their own income. Research by *Sangyong Hana, Gene C. Lai, and Chia-Ling Hoc* has analyzed the practice of placing insurance reserves in the United States, including: a conservative approach to insurance placement in the United States is important. The reason is that the principles of transparency of insurance reserves should be followed.

Otherwise, regulators will consider these investments harmful to shareholders and policyholders. With this in mind, the investment activities of insurance companies are strictly regulated [3]. *Chrysovalantis Gaganisa, Iftekhar Hasanb, Panagiota Papadimitrie, Menelaos Tasioueilmi* conducted research on the state of the insurance market after the financial and economic crisis, which showed that the demand for insurance showed high growth trends.

This, in turn, determines the level of risk in the investment portfolios of insurance companies. Properly organized investment policies by insurance companies play an essential role in this. Also, in recent years, in many developed countries, the policy of insurance companies to place reserves is supported by the state and creates new investment objects [4]. The role of the insurance market in the financial system in *A.M. Godin research*, insurance companies are becoming one of the major players in the financial market through their investment activities and potentials as well as providing insurance protection to various financial institutions. [5].

L.K. Ulibina's scientific article on the liberalization of the insurance market states that the main condition for the liberalization of the insurance market in the medium term is the development of long-term life insurance tools (types of insurance) that constitute domestic investment resources. In the context of international integration and financial globalization of the insurance market, it is necessary to develop processes (mechanisms) of integration into the domestic market to counteract the outflow of cash flows from national markets. The main principle in the process of integration with international trade and financial institutions is the free liberalization of the insurance market, taking into account the priorities of financial market development. *Shennayev Khojayor Musurmanovich*, an Uzbek scholar, wrote in his textbook "Insurance Case" that "Insurers convert passive funds received from various policy holders into active capital operating in the financial market." [6] expressed his views.

A.A. Kazakova gave her brief explanation in her research, about the problem of attracting individuals to the investment and insurance markets in the national financial markets. The integration of insurance and stock markets will lead to the development of investment insurance products. The development of such products segment of the general market will lead to the development of this financial market, as the stock market will attract deposits of the population and will be characterized by the development of long-term life insurance. Such a development will lead to the development of the national securities market as a whole [7].

Analysis and results: Insurance companies invest the proceeds of their activities in various sectors of the economy. Insurers are not only one-sided, they can not only generate investment and capital inflows into the financial market, but also directly work to improve the living conditions of the population. Here are some of them:

✚ Insurance ensures financial stability and reduces uncertainty by covering damages to all victims. In this way, the economic bankruptcy, economic employment, industrial accidents, the state reduces the fluctuations in the tax process.

✚ Voluntary pension insurance as one of the most important types of insurance ensures the security of the conditions of entry of these funds in the financial markets. The society will retain its ability to pay for future retirees by providing them with a stable monthly income for the rest of their lives based on their insurance premiums.

✚ By accumulating a small amount of money collected in the form of insurance premiums, insurance companies are able to finance large investment projects and thus have a positive impact on the economic growth of the country.

✚ Insurance provides the maximum risk of effective risk management and assessment. When investing, insurance companies carefully check the creditworthiness of creditors, and the borrower's information allows other investors in the market to get information as well. In general, careful monitoring of the level of risk by insurance companies ensures that the market is accurate.

✚ They can develop international trade among business representatives who do not have sufficient financial resources. That is, large insurance companies can invest the financial resources they receive from large businesses as an

investment in a company anywhere in the developing world. Thus, it contributes to the development of international trade between companies.

✚ Insurance companies try to regularly monitor the insured objects in an effort to maintain the safety of insurance premiums and maximize their profits. For example, for a fire-insured facility, insurance increases fire safety measures, which further reduces the level of risk that can occur and reduces the amount of losses in the community.

Funds from insurance funds reach different segments of society in different ways. The real potential of an insurance company to participate in investment activities depends on its potential. Potential, in turn, is a combination of financial resources located in a temporarily free state and used by investors in solving a task such as making a profit. The process of realization of potential in investments of the considered organizations is insurance of private capital and activity of insurance fund. The potential of the investment target is the area of the financial reserve, which remains after the reduction of costs, borrowings and insurance targets. In the case of an increase in the amount of the above payments, the investment potential may decrease with the growth of financial performance due to the increase in the size of the fund of the insurance organization and private capital. The investment activity of insurance companies is an additional source of income for the insurer, excluding the income from the insurance company. For many start-ups and non-startup insurance companies, investing in government securities is a good idea. As financial intermediaries, we can see the investment of the resources of insurance companies in all sectors of the economy in the following process in the European insurance market:

(Figure 1)

(The picture created by authoris based on sources from Insurance companies and the Financial Crisis)

Figure 1. Insurance companies investment activities in various sectors of the economy

As can be seen from the picture above, the investment activities of insurance companies are carried out in two directions. In the first, the funds will be directed to the real manufacturing sector, while in the second it will be directed to securities and bank deposits. It should be noted that in both cases, the investment program leads to positive changes in the life of the state and society. For example, infrastructure-oriented activities improve living conditions, improve investment attractiveness, and lead to more economic growth due to increased capital inflows. The same thing happens with investments in government securities. Proceeds from government bonds are redistributed to the population as a result of social transfers or public procurement. This, in turn, will lead to intensive economic growth. In recent years, insurance companies have accounted for almost half of all investments worldwide.

At a time when war and political games are not taking place, insurance savings are growing rapidly. Another factor that can be added to this is that insurance is done in cash, and money is the fastest growing financial instrument. Having such a large amount of financial resources, of course, not only increased the prestige of insurance companies, but also gave them a certain degree of dominance. A number of developed countries have developed their own laws and regulations on the placement of insurance reserves. This is due to the fact that the fast-growing insurance companies are able to catch up and diversify their capital in all areas. Below we consider the ratio of reserve placement in a number of countries, including Uzbekistan.

(Table 1)

Typesofassets:	Germany	France	Japan	USA	GreatBritain	Russia	Uzbekistan
Governmentsecurities						<15	unlimited
Government entities and municipal securities:	<30	<65	<30	<49	<2	<30	
Bankdeposits:						<50	<40
Investmentshares:						<10	
Sharesandbonds:				<4		<20	<30
Participation in the authorized fund and other assets					<60	<10	<30
Housingcertificates				<17	<2	<5	
RealEstate:	<20	<40	<20	<17	<20	<40	<50
Currencytransactions:						<10	
loans	<10	<50	<55	<4	<2		<10
Accountnumber:						unlimited	

(Table created by the author on the basis of "Finance and Credit")

Table 1. Standards for placement of reserves of insurance companies (% , percent)

Today, according to the experience of the world's leading companies, the company's investment portfolio includes 15% of investments in the authorized capital of enterprises and real estate, 25-60% of investments in securities, 15-30% of deposits in commercial banks, and other types of investments do not more than 1-12%. According to statistics, in 27 of the 100 largest industrial enterprises in the United States, this industry has a board of directors. With this indicator, insurance companies are second only to banks and investment organizations. But it is not surprising that in the next 10 years, insurance companies will own a large part of the industry. Most of the largest insurance companies today are located in the Asian region and their capitalization exceeds the annual gross domestic product of the average developed country. Below are examples of such large companies.

1. The AIA was founded in 1919 in Singapore. Headquartered in Hong Kong. This company's main activities are life insurance and other financial services. As of December 31, 2019, AIA's assets were \$ 284 billion and as of February 5, 2020, its market capitalization was \$ 126.2 billion.

2. AIG, or American International Group, has offices in 80 countries. Founded in Shanghai in 1919, the company is now headquartered in New York City. It mainly works in three segments: general insurance (commercial and personal insurance), life and retirement. The company owed the U.S. government \$ 180 billion due to the 2007-2008 financial crisis. But over the years, the company has recovered, with assets of \$ 525 billion and a market capitalization of \$ 45.2 billion.

3. Allianz was founded in 1890 in Germany. A leading financial services company providing products and services from insurance to asset management. Allianz serves customers in more than 70 countries. Insurance products range from property and accidents to health and life insurance products for corporate and individual clients. Allianz has a market capitalization of \$ 104.4 billion.

4. AXA is one of the leading insurance groups in the world, with more than 102 million customers and more than 125,000 employee bases in 56 countries. Its main activities are property and accident insurance, life insurance, savings and asset management. It was founded in 1816 when several insurance companies merged to form AXA. The company is headquartered in Paris, but has a large network in Africa, North America, Central and South America, Asia Pacific, Europe and the Middle East. The market size for the AXA Group is currently \$ 67 billion.

5. Berkshire Hathaway (BRK.A) was founded in 1889 and is associated with the name of Warren Buffett, who turned medium business into one of the largest companies in the world. Berkshire Hathaway is now a conglomerate of leading investment managers dealing in insurance through its affiliates, among other sectors such as rail transport, finance, utilities and energy, manufacturing, services and retail. The company's market capitalization reached a record \$ 554 billion and its assets exceeded \$ 817 billion. [8] In comparison, these figures are higher than the GDP of the average developed Asian countries. For example, in 2019, Thailand produced \$ 529.177 million, Malaysia \$ 365.303 million, the Philippines \$ 356.814 million, Vietnam \$ 261.637 million, and Singapore \$ 362.818 million. [9]

Of course, this large amount of money can support high investment processes. The level of development of countries also plays an important role in attracting insurance funds. For example, large investments are made in and out of Europe and the United States. The following chart shows the percentage of investment actions of insurance companies in European markets. (Figure 2)

(Diagram created by the author based on data from Insurance Europe; Philanthropy in Europe; Foundation Center)

Figure 2. Investment share of insurance companies in the European market (% , percent)

Based on the above data, insurance companies are leading the investment market with a clear figure of 51%. It is followed by pension funds with 24%. Needless to say, the majority of pension funds also belong to insurance companies. Retail businesses are in third place with 11 percent. However, it should be borne in mind that this is the sector that could be a serious competitor for insurance companies in the future, as e-commerce is booming. For example, Amazon, Ali Baba Group, E-Bay can now compete with any company in the world in terms of capitalization. Sovereign wealth funds followed with 4%, private investors with 8% and the once-thriving construction industry with 2% in the European market.

Conclusion:

In consequence of all the above analysis and research, we can conclude that the role of the stock market, including the share market, is to mobilize the free funds of the population, government and institutional investors and direct them to various sectors of the national economy , using them as the most important source of funding to stabilize the economy, improve money supply and increase incomes of the population and businesses. In this regard, the importance of insurance companies acting as institutional investors influencing the activity of the financial market, including the stock market, is important. The successful investment activities of insurance companies are vital in two ways. First, it is the basis for ensuring the financial stability of insurers. Second, the sources of investment, that is, the money collected by insurers, are one of the sources of economic growth in the state. With this in mind, we consider it expedient for insurance companies to do the following in order to establish a good investment policy:

- ✚ First, to provide insurance companies with more opportunities to avoid mergers, thereby increasing investment activity and achieving overall well-being;
- ✚ Second, the expansion of the insurance industry by creating new types of insurance activities, covering vacant funds and directing them to high-income sectors;
- ✚ Third, to further improve the insurance business, to participate in credit relations not only as insurance and investment programs, but also as a bank, and to change the insurance functions in accordance with modern requirements;
- ✚ Fourth, the use of digital platforms in the insurance industry, thereby saving money on insurance agents and employees, resulting in more efficient, affordable insurance services;

If the above recommendations are applied to insurance companies and organizations, we believe that their activities will change and they will be able to protect their losses from further risks in the life of society.

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